

Deliverable D3.3

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1 Executive summary

This document reports on the requirements for the use of structural biology data expressed by other research infrastructures (RIs) not directly operating in the field of structural biology. We complemented this information with a survey addressed to the structural biology community and beyond, to the general biological community, to obtain a user's perspective on this topic. RI representatives conveyed the need for innovative services that bridge structural information and the biomedical information that each RI is providing to its own reference communities. In parallel, individual researchers from the chemical, biological and biomedical communities expressed the need for tools that are more easily discoverable, better documented and affording a deeper comprehension of the quality of the underlying experimental data than currently available. In addition, the research community requested for improved reuse of structural data in complex scenarios such as modelling of biochemical events or in the interpretation of biological and functional information. This goes in the same direction as the aforementioned requirement of RI representatives that there should be tools that bridge structural information to other types of biomedically relevant information.

2 Detailed report on the deliverable

2.1 Gathering information from RIs

We leveraged the round table event that the West-Life and iNEXT projects co-organized in Brno, Czech Republic, on May 24th, 2017 in collaboration with Instruct (<https://www.structuralbiology.eu/content/bringing-together-the-bio-medical-scientific-communities-the-role-of-research-infrastructures>) to gather information from other RIs in the biomedical sciences on their possible use of structural biology data and how to facilitate it. To this end, we included the following questions among the topics for discussion that were circulated to the panellists:

- Are you aware of usage of structural biology data within your scientific domain? If yes, please specify;
- Is there a need / opportunity for initiatives that can support the exploitation of structural data by your users.

See D3.2 for details on the organization of the RT. The RT was open to all participants in the iNEXT annual meeting as well as to the participants in the subsequent biennial conference of Instruct.

The following RIs were represented at the RT:

1. ECRIN (Serena Battaglia)
2. EuroBioImaging (Antje Keppler)
3. ISBE (Vitor Martins dos Santos)
4. EATRIS (David Morrow)
5. EuOpenScreen (Bahne Stechmann)
6. Instruct, iNext (Lucia Banci, Susan Daenke)

Steve Brewer and Merlijn Van Rijswijk, representatives of two H2020 projects in the field of electronic research infrastructures (Edison and PhenoMeNal, respectively), and Hugh Lavery, Head of Scientific Operations of the IMI initiative, were also included in the RT panel.

The information relevant for the present report is based on the presentations of the panellists and the statements emerged during the open discussion as well as from informal discussions between West-Life representatives, including P7 Instruct, and the panellists.

2.2 Survey to the biological community

In order to obtain a better understanding of the opinion and requirements of the users' community of researchers active in structural biology or in the neighbouring biological and biomedical sciences, we designed the following survey

1. Are you aware of the structural data already available in public repositories (e.g. PDB, PDBe, EMDB, BMRB) and how to access them?
2. Do you think that the available tools for the use of structural data are suitable for non-expert users? If not, what is lacking or could be improved?
3. In your opinion, is there a need for initiatives that can support the exploitation of structural data by your users, e.g. by providing assistance with software tools?

4. What kind of structural data would be useful to your scientific community (raw structural data, metadata on structures and samples, 3D coordinates, ...)?
5. What kind of applications for structural data, if any, are in use in your scientific domain (please specify also the associated software tools)?
6. In your own scientific field, how are raw data and metadata (not in public repositories) made available to users?
7. What security/permissions, legal regulation is attached to data in your scientific domain?
8. Would it be useful for you to have a link to a specific site to access structural data or tools?
9. Please specify your scientific domain
10. In what field are you employed?
11. What is your gender?
12. What is your age range?

The survey was circulated to various mailing lists (about 5,000 recipients, although we could not check for redundancy in the lists), newsletters and was posted on the website of different RIs, including:

- CCP4BB mailing lists
- Instruct registered users
- Italian chemical society mailing list
- BioNMR mailing lists
- HADDOCK registered users
- PDB_REDO registered users
- The CORBEL web site
- The EuroBioImaging web site
- The ECRIN newsletter

The above list is in addition to the personal contacts and institutional web sites of the project partners.

2.3 Response from RIs

Several (EATRIS, EU-OPENSREEN, ISBE, ECRIN) but not all (excluding Instruct) representatives of Research Infrastructures and large projects that attended the Round Table mentioned in section 2.1 provided a direct reply to the discussion points circulated ahead of the event. Below we provide a summary of the feedback obtained from the replies as well as the subsequent discussion involving the audience in the room. We took into account also the results of the survey carried out by the 'Medical Infrastructure Users Forum' (MIUF) of the H2020-funded CORBEL project (available at <http://www.ecrin.org/sites/default/files/CORBEL/MIUF%20Survey%20Lay%20Report.pdf>).

RIs are keen on collaborations with structural biologists for specific purposes and/or selected themes. Examples include participation in grant consortia or collaborating for proposals of H2020 or other relevant funding programs. Further opportunities may arise in the context of fulfilling requests from private parties, such as SMEs, for targeted research projects. The natural fields of application involve drug development and medicinal chemistry. 3D structures are needed for structure-based drug development programs such as fragment screening and virtual screening. The lead compounds resulting from these could be further validated in the context of EU-OpenScreen infrastructure, whose offer involves experimental compound screening. Therefore, computational services in the field of structural biology would be complementary to the currently available offer. These services could be linked to the data available from ELIXIR, including the ChEBI databases for small molecule data and resources related to pathological mutations and other biomedical information. Similarly, systems biology models such as those developed by ISBE leverage structural information together with biological information available from ELIXIR in order to obtain mechanistic insights into the chemical bases of the effects observed by different perturbations of the modelled systems.

Some of the interactions and applications mentioned in the preceding paragraph, as well as the experimental structural studies that the users of the iNEXT project carry out, have the potential to unveil some of the mechanisms that are responsible for cellular malfunctions (hence disease) or for the beneficial effects of drugs. However, the link with clinical research is only indirect e.g. by providing information for clinical trials. In this respect, the discussion highlighted a few specific themes, namely coupling structural biology with pharmacology (drug efficacy and toxicity) in order to better predict drug efficacy ("smart" design), or the use of three-dimensional structures of proteins at the whole proteome level to predict toxic effects due to binding to a protein different from the target. As RIs are identified as resource providers for European Networks in

various thematic research and development areas (e.g. Instruct is a service provider and partner in Transvac2), the use of structural methods will be closely aligned with the project research objectives and available to users in the life and clinical sciences fields. Therefore, the continuation of this strategic approach to promote RI use should be supported.

2.4 Outcome of the survey

We received 216 responses from the survey described in Section 2.2. 10% of the respondents described themselves as having a medium-level or lower awareness of structural data and the associated public repositories. In agreement with this, 11% of the respondents were not familiar with any of the tools for the use of structural data. The survey addressed researchers with a broad area of expertise ranging from the field of structural biology chemistry to biophysics, and the above data indeed suggest that we were able to reach out to non-experts in structural biology. Even some respondents who reported to be highly aware of structural data were unfamiliar with the computational tools. Thus, the penetration of structural biology data and computational tools is not complete even within scientific disciplines very close to it. In addition, as many as 24% of the respondents thought that currently available computational tools are not suitable for non-experts. In the comments to this point, three major issues are outlined: a) there is no obvious guidance on which tools are better suited for a given task (“they are suitable but you need to know them, i.e.: which one do I have to use to answer my question”); b) the appropriate usage and main limitations of the various tools are not described with any clarity (“Structural analysis software remains difficult to use, while in theory it shouldn't be hard.”); c, current tools do not allow non-experts to appreciate how much the interpreted, final structural information is actually supported by the experimental data (“Visualization software don't show model limitations by default, therefore a non-expert tends to over-trust a macromolecular model”). 68% of the respondents indicated that there is a need for initiatives that can support the exploitation of structural data. According to comments, this could be implemented as collection(s) of tutorials, videos and webservers; some comments suggested a focus on data quality. Regarding the kind of data perceived as most useful, 3D coordinates, experiment metadata and raw data are the three most common suggestions (out of 181 provided). Better search capabilities and links to functional aspects e.g. via standardized bioinformatics analyses, have also been mentioned. The types of software tools already in use include mainly computational tools for structure visualization

and structure modelling, including docking, 44% of 194 responses indicated that the data and metadata that are not in public repositories provide information on the value of the data, ranging from completeness to reproducibility. Specific formats are typically used. There is modest awareness of legal and privacy issues related to data in our sample, based on the low number (108) of replies to this specific question. The large majority of these responses indicated that data are perceived as public and without any regulations attached to them. In a few cases IPR issues were mentioned (e.g. “publically funded research is required to be made publically available, but privately funded research can be protected.”). The availability of a specific site to access structural data or tools was deemed useful by 61% of the respondents.

About one quarter of all respondents declared to be professionally active in the field of structural biology. Other common disciplines were medicinal chemistry, biochemistry, biophysics and molecular biology. 68% of the respondents worked in University or higher education, 28% in research organizations, 5% in industry. The age distribution was relatively homogenous, except for the “24 or younger” range, with only three respondents (1.4%).

2.5 Overall conclusions

The feedback received from RI representatives and from the community of researchers in fields ranging from chemistry to molecular biology, indicates that the impact and awareness of structural biology as an enabling technology can be further improved. However, the types of requirements expressed by the RI representatives (typically project coordinators or project managers) and the individual scientists in the community differ significantly. RI representatives conveyed the need for innovative services that bridge structural information – typically three-dimensional structures – and the biomedical information that each RI is providing to its own reference communities. Such innovation would leverage both types of information to create new knowledge that goes beyond the sum of the individual parts. The desired knowledge is a fundamental one for a better understanding of health and disease, therefore indirectly relevant to clinical applications. The community view highlighted the lack of computational tools suitable to broaden the user basis and consequently the impact of structural biology. While currently available tools allow non-experts to visualize three-dimensional structures easily, they fail to provide indications on the quality of the experimental data supporting each structure and, perhaps more critically, they hinder the reuse of structural data in more complex scenarios, such as

modeling of biochemical events or in the interpretation of biological and functional information. To some extent, the latter aspect is not far from the requirement indicated by RI representatives that there should be computational tools that bridge structural information to other types of biomedically relevant information (see above).

In various cases, it could be argued that while the appropriate computational tools exist but are not widely adopted, an important action would be to facilitate their discovery and adoption; this in turn would result in better take-up of tools and/or in obtaining the necessary community feedback to improve their usability and usefulness. In other cases, the solutions could come from combining existing tools and sources of information by overcoming the barriers related to data exchange among them (e.g. format incompatibility, different semantics, etc.). Collecting and organizing currently available tools in order to facilitate access is a necessary first step before implementing future actions to extend them. This is in line with the overall strategy being implemented within the support activities of West-Life, whose aims include making the provision and use of advanced computational tools in integrated structural biology easier for end-users.

Annex 1: Survey questions

Structural Biology data for your research

This is a survey by the West-Life VRE

*Required

1. **Are you aware of the structural data already available in public repositories (e.g. PDB, PDBe, EMDB, BMRB) and how to access them? ***

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not at all	<input type="radio"/>	Fully aware				

2. **Do you think that the available tools for the use of structural data are suitable for non-expert users? If not, what is lacking or could be improved?**

Please use the "Other" field to provide suggestions

Mark only one oval.

- YES
- I am not familiar with any such tool
- NO
- Other: _____

3. **In your opinion, is there a need for initiatives that can support the exploitation of structural data by your users, e.g. by providing assistance with software tools?**

Please use the "Other" field to provide suggestions

Mark only one oval.

- NO
- I don't know
- YES
- Other: _____

4. **What kind of structural data would be useful to your scientific community (raw structural data, metadata on structures and samples, 3D coordinates, ...)?**

5. What kind of applications for structural data, if any, are in use in your scientific domain (please specify also the associated software tools)?

6. In your own scientific field, how are raw data and metadata (not in public repositories) made available to users?

Please use the "Other" field to provide suggestions

Mark only one oval.

- A specific format is needed
- Information on the value of the data (completeness, descriptors, reproducibility) is provided/needed
- Other: _____

7. What security/permissions, legal regulation is attached to data in your scientific domain?

8. Would it be useful for you to have a link to a specific site to access structural data or tools?

Please use the "Other" field to provide suggestions

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Maybe
- Other: _____

About You

The information you provide will remain confidential and can not be used to identify you.

9. Please specify your scientific domain *

10. In what field are you employed? *

Mark only one oval.

- University, higher education
- Industry
- Research organization
- Funding agency
- Other: _____

11. What is your gender

Mark only one oval.

- Female
- Male
- Prefer not to say

12. What is your age range

Mark only one oval.

- 24 or younger
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65 or older

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Annex 2: Graphical summary of replies

Below we report graphical summaries of responses to questions with a limited number of reply options, which can be summarized conveniently as pie charts. Annex 3 provides a link to a spreadsheet containing all responses, i.e. including also open questions.

Do you think that the available tools for the use of structural data are suitable for non-expert users? If not, what is lacking or could be improved?

215 responses

In your opinion, is there a need for initiatives that can support the exploitation of structural data by your users, e.g. by providing assistance with software tools?

215 responses

In your own scientific field, how are raw data and metadata (not in public repositories) made available to users?

194 responses

Would it be useful for you to have a link to a specific site to access structural data or tools?

210 responses

What is your age range

214 responses

Annex 3

Link to spreadsheet with the results of the survey:

<https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/onSHJxUWhFqTJ36>